

ISic3606

I.Sicily inscription 3606

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

natural rock

Object

rock

face

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Priolo Gargallo, hypogeum A, contrada Monachella

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Priolo Gargallo, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645680

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 57.0900

Bommara, T., Rizzone, V.G. 2007. Contributo alla conoscenza del territorio siracusano: recenti indagini a Priolo Gargallo. In Bonacasa Carra, R.M., Vitale, E. (eds.), *La cristianizzazione in Italia fra tardoantico e altomedioevo*. Palermo. pp.

1647-1672. At 1658

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